

Implementation of an Early Progressive Mobility Protocol in the ICU

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Background

- Intensive Care Unit–Acquired Weakness (ICU-AW) is a neuromuscular complication causing a critical illness associated with polyneuropathy and polymyopathy due to prolonged immobilization
- Early Progressive Mobility (EPM) protocol implemented in the ICU is proven to reduce ICU-AW by increasing patient mobility and in turn reduces ICU length of stay (LOS), time of mechanical ventilation (MV), and mortality

Problem

- Nurses are reluctant to mobilize ICU patients due to lack of education regarding the importance of mobility, patient weakness, the extent of critical illness, and increased risk for falls
- 40% of overall muscle strength and 14% of muscle mass can be lost in one week.
- Risks associated with immobility include fast functional decline, delirium, venous thromboembolisms, and decreased cardiac output

Purpose

To implement an EPM screening tool and protocol to improve patient mobility, reduce ICU LOS, and ultimately reduce the incidence of ICU-AW

Theoretical Framework

ACE Star Model of Knowledge Transformation

EPM Screening Tool and Protocol

Early Progressive Mobility Protocol

STEP 1: Screen for Safety
Evaluate daily

- M Myocardial Stability**
 - No active cardiac ischemia within past 12-24 h
 - No dysrhythmia requiring new anti-dysrhythmic agent within past 12-24 h
- O Oxygenation Stability**
 - F_{IO2} < 0.85 on mechanical ventilation
 - PEEP < 15 cm H₂O
 - No unsecured airway
- V Vasopressor Use**
 - No new or increase of any vasopressor for 2 h
- E Engages to Voice**
 - Responds to verbal stimulation
 - RASS < +3, or SAS < 6
- N Neuro Stability**
 - ICP < 15
 - No acute or uncontrolled intracranial event

Does not meet criteria = Start at Level 1 and evaluate in 12 h
Meets all criteria = Start at Level 2 and progress

STEP 2: Implement Progressive Mobility

1 LEVEL

Goal: Clinical stability and able to move arm against gravity

- Passive ROM 3 times a day
- Turn every 2 h
- Sitting position 20 min 3 times a day

2 LEVEL

Goal: Sitting upright and able to move leg against gravity

- Passive ROM 3 times a day
- Turn every 2 h
- Active-resistance PT
- Sitting position 20 min 3 times a day
- Sitting on edge of bed

3 LEVEL

Goal: Increased strength and stands with minimal to moderate assistance

- Turn every 2 h
- Active-resistance PT
- Sitting position 20 min 3 times a day
- Active transfer to chair >= 20 min 2 times a day

4 LEVEL

Goal: Strength and distance walk

- Self- or assisted turn every 2 h
- Active-resistance PT
- Active transfer to chair >= 20 min 3 times a day
- Ambulation (marching in place, walking in halls)

Methods

Design: Quality improvement to introduce a new EPM tool in the ICU
Setting: 36-bed ICU in Southern California
Sample: All ICU RNs (49 pre-education and 59 post-education)
Intervention: ICU RNs were educated over a 7-day period on utilizing & documenting EPM tool. Nurses were instructed to use new EMP tool for each patient & document BMAT score each shift
Data Collection: De-identified data collected on ICU LOS and BMAT scores before & after EPM tool implementation. EBPAS© and demographic survey administered pre & post implementation to gather ICU nurse demographic data and assess attitudes towards the EPM protocol

Limitations

- Nurses reluctant to mobilize ICU patients despite EPM protocol due to safety concerns
- Lack of improvement in BMAT scores could be related to insufficient charting or non-adherence to the EPM tool
- Post-survey results showed challenges in EPM protocol implementation due to Insufficient resources (46%), time constraints (23%), and lack of training (17%)

Recommendations

- Provide continued training on the use & safety of the EPM tool
- Enhance training resources by including tip sheets in education of EPM tool
- Introduce daily audits/mobility rounds to ensure every patient receives EPM
- Encourage use of Safe Patient Handling and Mobility (SPHM) technologies to safely mobilize patients
- Include physical therapists in EPM training as resource for mobility
- Expand EPM as a hospital-wide initiative
- Maintain staff commitment, interprofessional involvement, and organizational support for EPM tool implementation

References

EBPAS © and Demographics Analysis

EBPAS: Subscale 1- Requirements (p=.028)

Item	Pre Mean	Post Mean
11. Supervisor required	3.74	2.3
12. Agency required	3.8	2.32
13. State required	3.97	2.46

EBPAS: Subscale 3- Openness (p=.669)

Item	Pre Mean	Post Mean
1. I like to use new types of therapy/interventions	3.8	2.84
2. I am willing to try new types of therapy even if I have to follow a... by researchers.	3.95	2.95
4. I will try new therapy/interventions developed by researchers.	3.83	2.69
8. I would try a therapy/intervention even if it's different than usual	3.68	2.66

EBPAS: Subscale 2- Appeal (p=.525)

Item	Pre Mean	Post Mean
9. intuitively appealing?	3.73	2.68
10. it "made sense" to you?	3.9	2.82
14. used by colleagues who are happy with it?	3.8	2.46
15. enough training to use it correctly?	4	2.79

EBPAS: Subscale 4- Divergence (p=.240)

Item	Pre Mean	Post Mean
3. I know better than researchers how to care for clients.	2.44	1.19
5. Research based treatments/interventions are not useful.	2.34	1.16
6. Clinical experience is more important	3.12	1.83
7. I would not use manualized therapy/interventions.	2.3	1.12

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics: Total Participants (Pre-education 49; Post-education 59)

Measure	Pre-Education Percentage (N)	Post-Education Percentage (N)
Gender		
Female	67.3% (33)	71.2% (42)
Age		
21-40	67.4% (33)	59.3% (35)
41-60	8.2% (4)	30.5% (18)
61-80	4.1% (2)	8.5% (5)
Employment status		
Full-time	89.8% (44)	93.2% (55)
Part-time or Per diem	10.2% (5)	6.8% (4)
Level of Education		
Master's degree	10.2% (5)	11.9% (7)
Bachelor's degree	73.5% (36)	74.6% (44)
Associate degree	16.3% (8)	13.6% (8)
Years of Nursing Experience		
<2 years	34.7% (17)	30.5% (18)
2-10 years	34.7% (17)	35.0% (21)
10+ years	30.6% (15)	33.9% (20)
Years of ICU Experience		
<2 years	46.9% (23)	57.6% (34)
2-10 years	36.7% (18)	23.7% (14)
10+ years	16.3% (8)	16.9% (10)
Specialty Board Certification		
Yes	26.5% (13)	22.0% (13)

Results

AVERAGE ICU LOS (p=.450)

Average ICU BMAT SCORES (p=.336)

- Post-survey results showed 59% of nurses saw improvement in patient overall well-being
- Results of the t-test do not indicate statistical significance in ICU LOS or BMAT scores
 - ICU LOS decreased by 1.33 days (p=.450)
 - BMAT scores increased by 0.47 (p=.336)
- Results of independent t-test for EBPAS© Subscale 1 was statistically significant (p=.028) due to the EPM protocol becoming an ICU requirement

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